

ISSN 2181-9505
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy Universiteti
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi
Imom Buxoriy xalqaro ilmiy-tadqiqot markazi
O'zbekiston falsafa jamiyati

Национальный Университет Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека
Международный научно-исследовательский центр Имам Бухари
при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан
Философское общество Узбекистана

The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
Imam Bukhari International Research Center under the Cabinet of Ministers
of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Philosophical Society of Uzbekistan

**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
XALQARO JURNAL**

**ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ**

**PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL**

2023 № 1 (20)

Jurnal bir yilda 4 marta nashr qilinadi.
Журнал выходит 4 раза в год.
The journal is published 4 times in a year.

Toshkent-2023

SIYOSAT VA JAMIYAT FALSAFASI

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich

Liberalizm mafkurasi: genezisi, shakllanish omillari.....9-19

Shadiyev Bexzod Mirsalimovich

O‘zbekistondagi nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlar faoliyatini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....20-25

Alimatova Nargis Abduxalilovna

Raqobat mazmunining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi.....26-32

TA’LIM VA FAN FALSAFASI

Xidirov Mustafo Toyirqulovich

Abu Nasr Forobiy va Abu Ali ibn Sinoning bilish va faoliyat uyg‘unligiga oid tabiiy-ilmiy qarashlari.....33-40

Danilova V.S., Kojevnikov N.N.

Yevroosiyo madaniy kommunikatsiyalari va markazi: ontologik va metafizik jihatlari.....41-54

TARIX FALSAFASI VA FALSAFA TARIXI

Islamov Kamol Tashkulovich

Yevropa Uyg‘onish davri mutafakkirlari qarashlarida ijtimoiy-falsafiy fikrlar rivoji.....55-62

Burkhonov Sherzodbek Muxammadbobir ugli

Martin Xaydegger ta’limotidagi “Dasein” tushunchasi talqini.....63-68

Madalimov Timur Abduvaliyevich

Qadimgi Hindistonda Astika maktabining konseptual tahlili.....69-76

DUNYO MADANIYATI VA DINIY AN’ANALAR

Sagikizi Ayajan, Kakimjanova, Margarita Kabdulaevna, Qulibek Bagdatkali Abdimanapovich

Qozog‘iston jamiyatidagi ong transformatsiya sharoitlarida diniy qadriyatlar.....77-89

Saidzoda Daler Muxibullo

Zamonaviy jamiyat rivojlanishi sharoitlarida diniy-siyosiy ekstremizm tushunchasi tadqiqi.....90-98

Karimova Sadokat Tahirovna

Millatlararo totuvlikni ta’minlashda milliy o‘zlik va g‘urur tuyg‘ularining o‘rni.....99-109

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ПОЛИТИКИ И ОБЩЕСТВА

Хакимов Назар Хакимович

Идеология либерализма: генезис, факторы формирования.....9-19

Шадиев Бехзод Мирсалимович

Теоретические основы оптимизации деятельности неправительственных организаций в Узбекистане.....20-25

Алиматова Наргис Абдухалиловна

Историческая эволюция понятия соревнований.....26-32

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ

Хидиров Мустафо Тойиркулович

Естественно-научные воззрения Абу Наср Фараби и Абу Али ибн Сина о гармонии познания и деятельности.....33-40

Данилова В.С., Кожевников Н.Н.

Центры и коммуникации культуры евразии: онтологические и метафизические аспекты.....41-54

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ИСТОРИИ И ИСТОРИЯ ФИЛОСОФИИ

Исламов Камол Ташкулович

Развитие социально-философских мыслей в мнениях мыслителей эпохи Возрождения Европы.....55-62

Бурханов Шерзодбека Мухаммадбобир угли

Интерпретация понятия «Dasein» у Мартина Хайдеггера.....63-68

Мадалимов Тимур Абдувалиевич

Концептуальный анализ школы Астика в древней Индии.....69-76

МИРОВАЯ КУЛЬТУРА И РЕЛИГИОЗНЫЕ ТРАДИЦИИ

Сагикызы Аяжан, Какимжанова Маргарита Кабдулаевна, Кулыбек Багдаткали Абдиманопович

Религиозные ценности в условиях трансформации сознания в Казахском обществе.....77-89

Саидзода Далер Мухибулло

Исследование понятия религиозно-политического экстремизма в контексте развития современного общества.....90-98

Каримова Садокат Тахировна

Роль чувств национальной идентичности и гордости в улучшении межнациональной гармонии.....99-109

PHILOSOPHY OF POLITICS AND SOCIETY

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich

Ideology of liberalism: genesis, formation factors.....9-19

Shadiyev Behzod Mirsalimovich

Theoretical bases of the optimisation of the activities of non-governmental organizations in Uzbekistan.....20-25

Alimatova Nargis Abduxalilovna

Historical evolution of content of competition.....26-32

PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE

Khidirov Mustafo Toyirkulovich

The natural-scientific views of Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Ali Ibn Sina on the harmony of cognition and activity.....33-40

Danilova V.S., Kojevnikov N.N.

Centers and communications of eurasian culture: ontological and metaphysical aspects.....41-54

PHILOSOPHY OF HISTORY AND HISTORY OF PHILOSOPHY

Islamov Kamol Tashkulovich

Development of social and philosophical thoughts in the opinions of the Renaissance Thinkers.....55-62

Burkhonov Sherzodbek Muxammadbobir o'g'li

Interpretation of the concept of "Dasein" in Martin Heidegger.....63-68

Madalimov Timur Abduvaliyevich

A conceptual analyse of the astika schools in ancient India.....69-76

WORLD CULTURE AND RELIGIOUS TRADITIONS

Sagikizi Ayajan, Kakimjanova, Margarita Kabdulayevna, Qulibek Bagdatkali Abdimanapovich

Religious values in the conditions of transformation of consciousness in the Kazakhstan society.....77-89

Saidzoda Daler Muxibullo

Study of the concept of religious-political extremism in the context of the development of modern society.....90-98

Karimova Sadokat Tahirovna

Role of national identity, pride the emotions in improving interethnic harmony.....99-109

Karimova Sadokat Tahirovna,
Researcher, Department of Philosophy and
Spirituality, Faculty of Social Sciences,
National University of Uzbekistan
e-mail: karimovasadokat@mail.ru
(Tashkent, Uzbekistan)

ROLE OF NATIONAL IDENTITY, PRIDE THE EMOTIONS IN IMPROVING INTERETHNIC HARMONY

Annotation. In the study and development of the socio-spiritual image of the Uzbek people, it is appropriate to work based on the national identity and spiritual characteristics. That is why the socio-spiritual image of the Uzbek people is clearly manifested when compared with the sense of national identity, pride and pride. In fact, the core of the nation's socio-spiritual image is the awareness of national identity. However, it is distinguished by its complex meaning. Because the concepts of national and self-awareness, which form its core, are characterized by positive and negative situations. In this case, from a socio-philosophical point of view, nationality appears as a complex reality that reflects the structure of a particular nation, the language of the people, the location, social and cultural life, and the structure of the worldview. Self-awareness is determined by the feeling of being a part of this nationality.

Keywords: identity, ideology, nation, interethnic harmony, ethnogenesis

РОЛЬ ЧУВСТВ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИДЕНТИЧНОСТИ И ГОРДОСТИ В УЛУЧШЕНИИ МЕЖНАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ГАРМОНИИ

Аннотация. При изучении и развитии социально-духовного образа узбекского народа целесообразно работать исходя из национального самосознания и духовных особенностей. Именно поэтому социально-духовный облик узбекского народа ярко проявляется по сравнению с чувством национальной идентичности, гордыни и гордости. Фактически, ядром социально-духовного образа нации является осознание национальной идентичности. Однако оно отличается своим сложным смыслом. Потому что понятия национального и самосознания, составляющие его ядро, характеризуются позитивными и негативными ситуациями. В этом случае с социально-философской точки зрения национальность предстает как сложная

реальность, отражающая структуру той или иной нации, язык народа, местонахождение, социальную и культурную жизнь, структуру мировоззрения. Самосознание определяется ощущением принадлежности к этой национальности.

Ключевые слова: идентичность, идеология, нация, межнациональное согласие, этногенез.

MILLATLARARO TOTUVLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA MILLIY O'ZLIK VA G'URUR TUYG'ULARINING O'RNI

Annotatsiya. O'zbek xalqining ijtimoiy-ma'naviy qiyofasini o'rganish va rivojlantirishda milliy o'zlikni anglash va ma'naviy xususiyatlardan kelib chiqib ish olib borish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Shuning uchun ham o'zbek xalqining ijtimoiy-ma'naviy qiyofasi milliy o'zlikni anglash, g'urur va iftixor tuyg'ulari bilan solishtirganda yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Darhaqiqat, millatning ijtimoiy-ma'naviy qiyofasining o'zagini milliy o'zlikni anglash tashkil etadi. Biroq, u o'zining murakkab ma'nosi bilan ajralib turadi. Chunki uning o'zagini tashkil etuvchi milliylik, o'zlikni anglash tushunchalari ijobiy va salbiy holatlar bilan ajralib turadi. Bunda ijtimoiy-falsafiy nuqtai nazardan milliylik murakkab voqelik sifatida namoyon bo'lib, u muayyan millatning tuzilishi, xalqning tili, joylashuvi, ijtimoiy-madaniy hayoti, dunyoqarash tuzilishini aks ettiradi. O'z-o'zini anglash shu millatga mansublik hissi bilan belgilanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zlik, mafkura, millat, millatlararo totuvlik, etnogenез.

INTRODUCTION

With the independence, wide opportunities were created to realize the national identity. That is, wide opportunities have been opened to open powerful layers of human spirituality, high morals and national culture. As a result, spiritually beautiful and rich national customs and traditions were restored, the consciousness of our people towards their history changed in a positive direction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The realization of national identity is not limited to being proud of the heritage left by our ancestors, assimilating them, but it also covers the prevention of negative situations that are rapidly entering our lives. Therefore, the main direction of national identity awareness is determined by achieving a worthy contribution to the system of universal human values with achievements in the field of spiritual values, science and technology.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

As a result of his research, J.Bahranov said, "The realization of national identity is closely related to ethnogenesis. Without knowing the ethnogenesis, it is impossible to perceive the features of national identity". With this opinion, the author wants to prove that the awareness of national identity is related to the ethnos of each nation. He also pays special attention to the issue of the individual's

national identity. According to the author, "Understanding the national identity of a person means, first of all, belonging to a certain nation (ethnic group), knowing the historical place of this nation in the development of humanity, loyalty to national values, understanding the current needs and interests of one's nation (ethnic group), knowing the ways of its future development. and it is understood that he serves conscientiously for this purpose.

In fact, national identity is determined by ethnological factors. However, it becomes more refined on the basis of changes in spiritual and cultural quality. Also, the potential to be proud of the sense of nationality, national pride, national consciousness, national pride, the rich history of one's nation, its spiritual and educational heritage, and its contribution to world civilization is of great importance in the realization of national identity. National pride is the main driving force in this process, and it serves to realize and preserve identity. The quality of belonging to the nation in our people is connected with life and existence, and it is embedded in the blood and consciousness of our people and constitutes the main content of spirituality and enlightenment.

S. Otamurodov's doctoral dissertation is characterized by the unique analysis of the national identity, its philosophical content and importance as an important symbol of the nation. Based on his research, the author interprets the understanding of the nation's national identity as "... confirmation as a carrier of certain material and spiritual values, understanding of belonging to language, culture, customs, traditions and values". It can also be observed that the issue of national identity was consistently developed in the author's subsequent works. For example, in his later work, the author classifies the concept of national identity as follows: "Each nation (Elat) considers itself a real entity, representing certain material and spiritual wealth, a single language, customs, traditions, values and belonging to the state, interests and Understanding the commonality of needs is called understanding of national identity. It is clear from this opinion that the process of realizing national identity is not just wishful thinking. Also, achieving independence is not enough for this. That is, in order for the nation to realize its national identity, it is required to restore spiritual values, effectively use its opportunities and advantages, and solve problems in the spiritual and educational sphere. After all, no one recognizes a person who does not know himself, that is, who does not realize his identity, who does not have his own dignity, who does not have his own national and spiritual image, and the people. Therefore, the independence of a person's thoughts and the independence of the country begins with the realization of this identity. Self-awareness, that is, self-awareness, begins with thinking, creative independent thinking. In this, the role of historical knowledge with an objective basis is of incomparable importance.

After all, "Awareness of national identity is formed along with historical and cultural development in ethnogenesis. With the establishment of the historical-cultural core, the people and the nation clearly feel their place in existence, or rather, in world processes. This is an important sign of national identity."

With the honor of independence, our country has been at the stage of development in all aspects during the following years, showing its age-old lifestyle, cultural-educational image, and national traditions that have survived for centuries. In this place, concepts such as traditions, values, traditions and customs are manifested in the life of ordinary people and express their goals, objectives, qualities, and signs. That is, we have such opportunities in front of us now that we need to critically evaluate our historical path, determine the foundations of our national statehood, return to the veins of our great culture, the roots of our ancient heritage, and apply the rich traditions of our past in building a new society.

"Historical memory plays a very important role in the process of restoring the impartial and true history of the nation, the beloved country, the territory of our country, the realization of national identity, so to speak, national pride."

"For about a century and a half, the founders of the ideas of socialism and communism and their fans tried to convince humanity that their theories are true and perfect." Language is an important element of the socio-spiritual image of the nation. In this sense, the preservation of the purity of the Uzbek language will have an impact on the process of realizing the national identity, its consistency, as well as the further development of the social and spiritual image of the nation.

Based on the above points, it can be understood that depriving a nation of its language is equivalent to depriving it of its spirituality. After all, in such a situation, the people who have lost their national language will first of all move away from speaking their mother tongue. This leads to the moral decline of the people. Secondly, the national language loses its purity, its status declines as a result of the narrowing of the scope of its functions. As a result, the national language, which is considered the main spiritual and educational factor determining the existence of the nation, falls into a "dead" state. The national language is a means of uniting the nation spiritually. This feature of the language is determined by its expression of the nation's way of life and thinking, cultural experience, and the path of development. In this sense, K. Khanazarov said, "The national language is unique in this sense, its vocabulary, vocabulary, different aspects of human consciousness, different shades of human emotions. "You will feel that it is unique in its inner environment," he writes.

However, the feeling of patriotism is not the same for everyone. That is why "the level of feeling of patriotism among some Uzbeks cannot be said to be at the level of demands for national independence. Not everyone understood that the responsibility of preserving, protecting and developing Uzbek culture and its spirituality lies with the people living in this republic as a nation. Struggle to acquire new equipment and technology, to be a devotee of science, to cultivate entrepreneurial qualities, to appreciate national language and culture, to master military art, all these are practical manifestations of patriotism. Therefore, language is an important factor that participates in the process of self-realization of each nation by forming national pride and pride.

The highest sign of spirituality is patriotism. Patriotism is the main goal, mission, and highest value of the national idea. It is extremely important to educate the young generation in the spirit of patriotism, to strengthen the feelings of national pride, independence and loyalty to the Motherland in the minds of our

people. From this point of view, the main direction of enlightenment is to educate the young generation in the spirit of patriotism. After all, any science should serve the interests of the people, the nation, and the development of the country. The subject who spreads such knowledge is a selfless person. There is a great need for such people in the transition period or in the current globalization. In this sense, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, said, "Especially those who have taken on these extremely complex and responsible tasks in all eras, are abandoning old patterns, are opening new ways in this field, and are working tirelessly to further enrich people's worldview." [Karimov I.A., 1996] "We should widely support the aspirations and practical actions of selfless people, which are not visible at first glance, but require great diligence, knowledge and experience, and we should create all-round conditions for them to achieve effective results," he writes.

Difficulties, obstacles, imbalances, and even the increase of criminal activities during the transition to the market economy could not extinguish the feeling of the Motherland in the heart of a person of pure conscience, if it has become a deep belief. However, as long as there are social groups with diverse goals and interests, different and sometimes contradictory perceptions of the common goal will remain. There has never been an absolutely ideal state or system anywhere. The birth of new generations brings new problems to the society; it is this continuity and gradualness that ensures the continuous and gradual continuation of social life. Therefore, by forming a sense of patriotism in the transitional generations, the tasks in this regard are not fully fulfilled, but it is a foundation for new tasks in the new stage of enlightenment. That's why many centers of enlightenment are being built in order to deeply inculcate the ideas of independence, national pride and patriotism in the hearts and minds of our people, especially the young generation. Now, developing and clearly systematizing their socio-spiritual mission, spiritual-ethical programs of activities conducted in these places, and raising them to the level of value for the future generation is also an important task. Because these complexes provide an impetus for the spiritual development of the nation.

And the love of a person for the homeland is the creation of material wealth of the people in a certain area, the achievement of spiritual and moral perfection, the development of science, a unique independent way of life, culture, traditions, language, religion, national borders and army, territory, natural resources, national It is manifested in keeping statehood, carefully guarding it, deeply studying its historical actions for further development, being loyal to it, living for the present and future generations, working hard, showing selflessness and enthusiasm.

However, the national idea, the concept of patriotism, which is an integral part of it, is not an idea that can be forced into people's minds. It is based on our national characteristics and universal values, our great history. So, these views are in our blood, we just need to bring them to the surface. In order to convey these ideas to the minds of our youth, our people, education and upbringing, science - science, cultural - educational, literature and art, religious and physical education institutions, besides, residents of the neighborhood, each family, are required to be cohesive and active around this ideology.

It has already become clear that it is impossible to build a new society, new socio-historical relations and a new worldview without raising the national values to a higher level. That is why "From the first days of our independence," wrote the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, "restoration of the huge, priceless spiritual and cultural heritage created by our ancestors over many centuries has become an extremely important task that has risen to the level of state policy." [Karimov I.A. 1997] We believe that it is an organic, natural process consisting of the growth of self-awareness, the return to the spiritual roots of the nation and its roots.

In order for a person to be free, independent and complete, he must be able to feel, perceive, understand the world, himself, learn its laws, realize that he is a part of this world and his place in it. This is how he works honestly and becomes spiritually pure. Then a person contributes to building a free and prosperous Motherland, a free and prosperous life, and considers himself responsible for it. After all, as the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, said, "Pride of one's country and patriotism of citizens helped many countries in the world reach advanced levels." Therefore, the national pride in people's hearts is a great spiritual force that affects the development of their feelings of love for the Motherland.

As a result of not understanding national pride or consciously denying it, ignoring it, considering it not an important issue, it ultimately leads to ideological convulsions, instability, indeterminacy, hesitations. National pride is a great feeling that defines the nation's past, present and future, and its fundamental interests. Based on this feeling, the representatives of the conscious nation should be ready to throw themselves into fire and water without hesitation.

National pride is formed on the basis of the historical memory of each nation, that is, it comes from the realization that the material and spiritual heritage left from ancestors to generations is huge and important in front of others. Also, national pride creates a feeling of pride in one's nation, instills a sense of pride in one's ancestors and their great services. For this reason, national pride plays an important role in shaping the social-spiritual image of a representative of each nation. For this reason, the Uzbek nation has achieved certain achievements in restoring its national pride. In this regard, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, writes as follows: "The proof of this is spiritual growth, the restoration of the ancient values of our people, at the same time, the introduction of democratic relations and free market principles, the search for the worldview and thinking of our people, entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship, their own We can observe the virtues of living based on one's own strength, intelligence, knowledge and experience, and the feeling of confidence in the future is getting stronger and stronger." After all, it is the need of the hour to involve a perfect person, a representative of the nation, who has pure and high national pride, strong physically and mentally.

We can never forget the possibilities of our national state, its compatibility with our national interest in various relations with other countries. It is known from the history of some foreign countries that their external appearance, opinions, speeches, and personal documents are associated with the name of a national

republic, but their actions, inner feelings, personal interests, and behavior are limited to narrow interests. As a result, the work of protecting the important state interest entrusted to him is paralyzed or goes into crisis. Today, we are glorifying the Uzbek people to the world as a great nation based on our historical memory, and in fact it is. In general, there is not a single nation in the world that does not consider itself great. Because every nation has its own history and past. In recent years, as a proof of our opinion, various conferences have been organized to conduct research on the study of the national and spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, to once again introduce our old and modern cities to the world. The goals of such events were to tell the world how great people our ancestors were, how they made an incomparable contribution to the development of world science through various fields of science, and how our region is one of the great ancient centers of world civilization. Also, the enthusiasm, high intelligence, entrepreneurship and leadership of our grandfathers will always be an example for our people, especially for the young generation. In this sense, to bring to light the work of our ancestors who worked hard for the sake of my people, for my country, thought about the future, fought for the freedom of our country, sacrificed their lives for the development of our nation, left prosperous cities and oases, unique beautiful monuments, to appreciate them, to make their souls happy, to continue their noble work. It is the biggest task of today's generation for us.

The importance of independence in restoring national pride is immeasurable. Independence increases people's national pride and enriches it with the sense of responsibility towards the nation, the Motherland, and the memory of ancestors. In such conditions, being proud of the independence of our country, working honestly to build a free, free, prosperous life in our country, achievements before the world community, and the use of universal technologies are factors that increase national pride. This, in turn, determines the strength, potential, creative activity of our compatriots in many ways, mobilizes them to constantly search for the formation of a healthy sense of national pride.

A. Achildiev said that "the system of perceptions of the unity and integrity of the representatives of the nation, connected by the totality of the territory, socio-economic and cultural relations, is the realization of the national identity." This feeling is also characterized by calling the youth to mobilize their strength, abilities and talents for national and universal benefits.

The high national value, honor and glory of the Uzbek people is based on their kindness and pure conscience. In particular, Uzbeks have accepted religion, honor, and shame as important virtues in all aspects of social life. It has such qualities that sometimes it is called only "Uzbek virtue".

"Sharq taronalari" music festival has become a tradition in the charming city of Samarkand, one of the cradles of world civilization, where different cultures meet. The fact that this music conference has gained attention in the international arena and annually attracts many artists not only from the East, but also from the West, shows that it is gaining a great tradition and great prestige in a short period of time.

The first reforms in our country were also aimed at educating a perfect person and bringing up worthy heirs of our future.

One of the manifestations of national pride is expressed in respect and pride in traditions and values created by the genius of our people. Today, human kindness is a priority in our country. Both young and old look to the future with great hope and full confidence. The most important thing is that our country is peaceful and our people are happy with their peaceful life. The revival of our national traditions, the polishing of our customs, the spiritual image of our people is becoming more beautiful.

National pride is clearly expressed in preserving and respecting the material and spiritual heritage of one's nation. We know that reforms will succeed when the immortal rich spiritual heritage and teachings of our forefathers, our best traditions are revived. Because only educated, mentally strong and physically strong people take bold steps on the path of independence and development.

In this process, B. M. Ochilova stated that "even in the study of the heritage of ancestors, it is important to refrain from absolutizing it or worshiping the past, not to belittle the value of the spiritual heritage, to strictly observe scientific objectivity and standards." Our people should be interested in the heritage of their ancestors. Noble feelings such as purity, honesty, conscientiousness, kindness, which are the constant motto of our ancestors, do not appear in our people by themselves.

A. Achildiev said that "the system of perceptions of the unity and integrity of the representatives of the nation, connected by the totality of the territory, socio-economic and cultural relations, is the realization of the national identity." This feeling is also characterized by calling the youth to mobilize their strength, abilities and talents for national and universal benefits.

The high national value, honor and glory of the Uzbek people is based on their kindness and pure conscience. In particular, Uzbeks have accepted religion, honor, and shame as important virtues in all aspects of social life. It has such qualities that sometimes it is called only "Uzbek virtue".

"Sharq taronalari" music festival has become a tradition in the charming city of Samarkand, one of the cradles of world civilization, where different cultures meet. The fact that this music conference has gained attention in the international arena and annually attracts many artists not only from the East, but also from the West, shows that it is gaining a great tradition and great prestige in a short period of time.

The first reforms in our country were also aimed at educating a perfect person and bringing up worthy heirs of our future.

One of the manifestations of national pride is expressed in respect and pride in traditions and values created by the genius of our people. Today, human kindness is a priority in our country. Both young and old look to the future with great hope and full confidence. The most important thing is that our country is peaceful and our people are happy with their peaceful life. The revival of our national traditions, the polishing of our customs, the spiritual image of our people is becoming more beautiful.

National pride is clearly expressed in preserving and respecting the material and spiritual heritage of one's nation. We know that reforms will succeed when the immortal rich spiritual heritage and teachings of our forefathers, our best traditions

are revived. Because only educated, mentally strong and physically strong people take bold steps on the path of independence and development.

In this process, B. M. Ochilova stated that "even in the study of the heritage of ancestors, it is important to refrain from absolutizing it or worshiping the past, not to belittle the value of the spiritual heritage, to strictly observe scientific objectivity and standards." Our people should be interested in the heritage of their ancestors. Noble feelings such as purity, honesty, conscientiousness, kindness, which are the constant motto of our ancestors, do not appear in our people by themselves.

One of the aspects that express national pride is the ability to show love for one's nation in practical activities. There is a wise proverb in our people. "What a man does, a man can do." As we mentioned above, we are descendants of creative people. Our people are capable of everything, there is nothing they cannot do. In this sense, "...introduction of the world's advanced technologies in the life of our country, every boy and girl who has fire in their hearts should use all their skills and serve for this dear Motherland." Thanks to the creator, today Uzbek products from cars, buses to airplanes can be found in different parts of the world. To be honest, I was very proud to see Uzbek boys learn to drive the most complex machines. In general, the so-called Uzbekistan, where we live and work, is peaceful, people are friendly and harmonious, if we agree with each other in every house and family, make compromises, keep our heads together and live peacefully, it is not a question to overcome any obstacles.

The brave sons of the nation, like Najmuddin Kubro and Jalaluddin Manguberdi, prefer to give up their lives in defense of their beloved country, not to save their lives. This is a clear expression of self-awareness, self-sacrifice for the country, Motherland, people. As noted, national pride and national self-awareness are interrelated in terms of content and essence, they enrich and complement each other, one cannot exist without the other.

All the historical monuments that were the pride and pride of the nation, showing what their forefathers were capable of, were destroyed and completely neglected. The science labs were turned into warehouses. Only with the honor of independence, our nation got the opportunity to study its history fairly, objectively and objectively. We began to be spiritually nourished by the ancient and rich history of our nation, the wisdom and life teachings of our great scholars, creative ideas, and ways of life. That is why history is called a great teacher, source of education and inspiration.

"In its foreign policy, Uzbekistan follows principles such as cooperation with all countries on the basis of equal rights and mutual interest, non-interference in their internal affairs, loyalty to universal human values, preservation of peace and security, priority of international law and norms."

As the first President I. Karimov said, "Truly, if the nation wants to see its future, its memory should always be awake. Because if the people and the nation do not draw the necessary conclusions and lessons from the life of yesterday, from the difficult and difficult days it has passed, from the tests of history, it will lose its way again in the future and face a crisis." [Karimov I.A. 2000] We have not yet forgotten the bitter fate of the recent history and should not forget it. After all, it is

not difficult to imagine the situation of a nation that has lost its entire history, body, and identity. Unfortunately, this period is also a part of our history, may God protect us from such dark days. We live with lessons from every moment of this period, we are afraid of making mistakes again. As the inheritors of the great historical memory, our hearts are full of pride and pride from the deeds of our ancestors, and we continue to move forward towards our great goals.

When the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov wrote that "National pride and national pride should be the foundation of all our work", he showed how important these ideas are for our nation, and these feelings are shared by every person living in this country, every citizen. that it becomes the biggest support and the biggest trust for each of us wants to emphasize. [Karimov I.A., 1996] It is also necessary to respect the history, culture and value of other nations with a sense of national pride in people's minds. Because, in the conditions of the current globalization, creating a sense of belonging and responsibility for all events happening in the world and constantly strengthening it is one of the priority tasks. That is why, in addition to the knowledge of the history of their country and people, it is necessary for the current growing youth and the next generation to study the achievements of world history and culture in depth. All such activities are important for the future of our nation.

It is known that the impartial and truthful recovery of complex and still undiscovered realities in the history of each nation, awareness of national identity, restoration and growth of national pride are very important in our modern literature and art. Therefore, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, said: "If we want to glorify our Uzbekistan to the world, glorify its ancient history and bright future, and keep it forever in the memory of generations, we must first educate great writers, great poets, great artists." writes Because, by educating such poets and creators, by reforming and renewing the life of the society, it is possible to re-open the social-spiritual image of the nation from different layers. In turn, the great works created by them created the ground for a sharp change in the mentality of the Uzbek people, especially the youth, towards patriotism, national pride, and tolerance for the whole world. This brought about important changes in the mentality of the Uzbek people. These changes are so bright and unique that it does not shy away from integration in the conditions of globalization, on the contrary, it helps to become an integral part of the world community.

CONCLUSION

First of all, the deepening of the awareness of national identity, the inculcation of the national idea in the minds of the people, the formation of feelings of national pride and pride in taking a strong place in spiritual life will help to realize important social functions in raising the young generation to be perfect human beings. Also, they help to form the feeling of honoring the rich social and spiritual heritage, national and spiritual values of our people, and being proud of them. It is the sense of national identity that helps to preserve the spirit of self-reliance in citizens, to form a culture of self-criticism and tolerance to criticism, as well as to understand that they are the heirs of great scientists and

creators who made an unforgettable contribution to world civilization and shine like stars in the sky of thought.

Secondly, awareness of national identity, pride in national pride, pride in one's nation's rich history, spiritual and educational heritage, and its contribution to world civilization create ample opportunities to further increase one's potential. National pride is the main driving force in this process, and it serves to realize and preserve identity. After all, the characteristic of belonging to the nation in our people is connected with life and existence, and it is embedded in the blood and soul of our people and constitutes the main content of spirituality and enlightenment.

In particular, "The situation of religious freedom and inter-ethnic harmony in our country has improved radically. The core of our activities in this regard is "Establishing the principle that tolerance, international harmony is a factor of development". We are carrying out extensive work to further strengthen inter-ethnic harmony and inter-religious tolerance. July 30, designated as International Friendship Day by the UN General Assembly, was announced as "People's Friendship Day" in our country and we celebrated it widely in 2021. I am confident that he will become a good man and serve our people even more under the flag of our Motherland."

Helping our republic will help to effectively use religion as a factor of high culture and spirituality, morals and morals in the creation of renewals and changes in the country's worldview, internal spiritual environment. The population has a unique sphere of influence in the country's management system. As a result of the study of inter-ethnic and inter-religious problems, any aggregate can be developed. It is clear that calling an ethnically diverse society a multicultural society is acceptable.

BIBLIOGRAPHIES

1. Karimov I.A. Vatan sajdagoh kabi muqaddasdir. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 1996.
2. Karimov I.A. Yangicha fikrlash va ishlash – davr talabi / I.A.Karimov. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 1997.
3. New encyclopedic dictionary. – M.: 2004. – S. 12-16.
4. Mirziyoyev Sh. New Uzbekistan strategy. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2021. – 306
5. Tishkov V.A. O tolerantnosti // Tolerantnosti i soglasie. Materialy international conference. – Yakutsk, 1995. – S 19.